

1 **YAP1 has functions in pluripotency.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of YAP1 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human embryonic
11 stem cells.

12 Citations

13 1. Frum, T., Murphy, T.M. and Ralston, A., 2018. HIPPO signaling resolves embryonic cell fate
14 conflicts during establishment of pluripotency in vivo. *Elife*, 7, p.e42298.

15 2. Hashimoto, M. and Sasaki, H., 2019. Epiblast formation by TEAD-YAP-dependent expression of
16 pluripotency factors and competitive elimination of unspecified cells. *Developmental cell*, 50(2),
17 pp.139-154.